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	Contributors:	Caspar van Leeuwen (SURF), Casper van Leeuwen (SURF), Paul Melis (SURF), Kenneth Hoste (UGent), Lara Peeters (UGent), Alan Ó Cais (UB), Thomas Röblitz (UiB)
	Reviewed by:	Caspar van Leeuwen (SURF), Kenneth Hoste (UGent)
	Approved by:	Alan O'Cais (UB)

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¹satish.kamath@surf.nl

²maksim.masterov@surf.nl

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Executive Summary

The European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) test suite described in Deliverable 1.5 is deployed on various platforms in two phases, namely (i) the pre-deployment phase and (ii) the post-deployment phase. These platforms include the cloud such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), EuroHPC systems such as Vega and Karolina, National Tier 1 systems such as Snellius (The Netherlands), Hortense (Belgium) and Betzy (Norway) and National Tier 2 systems such as Fram (Norway). Pre-deployment testing is performed before the application is ingested into EESSI software stack and post-deployment testing is performed in a periodic manner on various systems listed in this deliverable.

The purpose of the pre-deployment test step is not only to test the software itself but also to test that the underlying libraries that are used by the software are also working in a sane manner on a given hardware architecture. A mapping is implemented between the software to be ingested and the tests to be executed. Of course, this testing is designed to consume minimal resources while testing the software, some of its components (if applicable), and another application from the stack to check if the installation affects them.

The post-deployment tests are periodically run on various systems listed in this deliverable. The results of these tests are automatically ingested into a database and can be visualized using a dashboard. The technical details of the database ingestion pipeline, the design of the dashboard, its views and other aspects such as storage, security etc. are discussed in detail within this deliverable. The results of the test suite show the indicative performance of a particular software that can be achieved on a given hardware. The dashboard provides a platform to analyze this indicative performance on various hardware as a time series and perform a comparative analysis across different systems. This is not only useful for the end-users, but also for the system maintainers and administrators.

To summarize: the developed test suite is deployed across various systems to collect indicative performance data and a dashboard is developed for the analysis and continuous monitoring of the EESSI software stack.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This deliverable aims to describe the periodic tests that are running via the developed portable test suite described in Deliverable 1.5, running on several European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC) systems as well as in our Continuous Integration (CI) bot. The primary purpose of running periodic tests is to check the performance of the EESSI software stack in a time series and provide the results to the users so that performance expectations for various software can be set on different hardware for the users on different systems. To do this in an efficient manner, a test suite dashboard (also described in this document) is developed where the performance of the EESSI software stack can be checked on various systems and compared.

1.2 Target audience for this deliverable

This deliverable is targeted at readers with experience in High Performance Computing (HPC) system support and HPC end-users, particularly in the context of maintaining and testing software stacks (or specific applications) for HPC infrastructure.

1.3 Deliverable outline

Section 2 describes how the EESSI test suite is deployed as a test step in the software deployment pipeline and as periodic runs where the installed software are tested on various hardware platforms. The data produced by these periodic runs are collected in a database and can be visualized using a dashboard whose development and technical details are described in Section 3. Furthermore, Section 4 describes the potential usage of the deployed test suite and the data collected from periodic runs, through the dashboard, by end users, system maintainers, and administrators.

1.4 Partner contributions

SURF and UGent contributed as planned to the work in this deliverable. Note that Task 5.3 had other partners (RIJK-SUNIGRON, Uib, Ub), who contributed to the development of the pre-deployment pipeline and to the deployment of the test suite (as periodic runs) in various systems both at the national and EuroHPC level.

2 Deployments

Due to the separation of system-specific and test-specific information, the EESSI test suite (described in deliverable 1.5) can be deployed on any system, while only requiring that one write a ReFrame configuration file that describes the specifics of that system.

There are two ways in which the test suite is used within the MultiXscale project:

1. In the test step of the deployment pipeline to add new software to EESSI.
2. Regular runs on a large variety of HPC systems providing EESSI.

2.1 Running the test suite as part of the EESSI deployment pipeline

All EESSI software is built by the EESSI build bots (see [1]). Bot instances are running on a variety of systems: from Magic Castle clusters in AWS and Azure, to HPC clusters from MultiXscale partners (e.g. at SURF and UGent), to EuroHPC clusters (e.g. on Deucalion, and in preparation for JUPITER).

The bot configuration describes which partitions a bot instance can submit to. For example, the EESSI build bot running on the AWS Magic Castle cluster is configured with:

```

1 arch_target_map = {
2     "linux/x86_64/generic" : "--partition x86-64-generic-node",
3     "linux/x86_64/intel/haswell" : "--partition x86-64-intel-haswell-node",
4     "linux/x86_64/intel/sapphirerapids" : "--partition x86-64-intel-srapids-node",
5     "linux/x86_64/intel/skylake_avx512" : "--partition x86-64-intel-skylake-node",
6     "linux/x86_64/intel/cascadelake" : "--partition x86-64-intel-caslake-node",
7     "linux/x86_64/intel/icelake" : "--partition x86-64-intel-icelake-node",
8     "linux/x86_64/amd/zen2" : "--partition x86-64-amd-zen2-node",
9     "linux/x86_64/amd/zen3" : "--partition x86-64-amd-zen3-node",
10    "linux/aarch64/generic" : "--partition aarch64-generic-node",
11    "linux/aarch64/neoverse_n1" : "--partition aarch64-neoverse-n1-node",
12    "linux/aarch64/neoverse_v1" : "--partition aarch64-neoverse-v1-node" }

```

The build pipeline that the bot runs has three stages: a build stage, a test stage, and a deploy stage. To be able to run the test step, a ReFrame configuration file is required that matches the partitions for which the bot is configured. For example, the section for the Intel Skylake nodes on this cluster would look like this in the ReFrame configuration file:

```

1 {
2     'name': 'x86_64_intel_skylake_avx512',
3     'scheduler': 'local',
4     'launcher': 'mpirun',
5     'access': ['--nodes=1', '--ntasks-per-node=16', '--partition x86-64-intel-skylake-node'],
6     'environs': ['default'],
7     'features': [
8         FEATURES.CPU
9     ] + list(SCALES.keys()),
10    'resources': [
11        {
12            'name': 'memory',
13            'options': ['--mem={size}'],
14        }
15    ],
16    'extras': {
17        # Make sure to round down, otherwise a job might ask for more mem than is available
18        # per node
19        EXTRAS.MEM_PER_NODE: 31342,
20    },
21    'max_jobs': 1
22 },

```

We don't run the full test suite in the test step: if there are tests in the EESSI test suite for the software that is being added, we run those. In addition, we run a small number of tests to make sure the installation does not inadvertently break other components of the software stack. A mapping is done between which software is being installed, and the corresponding set of tests from the EESSI test suite that should be run for this software.

2.2 Periodic runs

Periodic testing of applications within the EESSI software stack is setup on various EuroHPC systems as well as local Tier 1 systems, and also in the cloud. In any cluster, the performance of a certain software depends on performance

of various system level components such as the OS-level stack, the compilers/toolchains, the intermediate math libraries and finally application level software and its dependencies. The primary purpose of the testing is to check the performance of the software provided by the EESSI stack which mainly covers everything above the OS-level stack. Furthermore, since the software stack is being tested on various different systems, observations regarding the systems themselves can be drawn from the data which is collected and displayed in the dashboard. These will be covered in section 4.

2.2.1 Testing setup

These tests are set up using the cron jobs on the login nodes of the systems and then the test results are pushed to the dashboard storage via an ingestion script. Based on the resource availability, the frequency and scale of the tests are defined. The daily tests are limited to a maximum scale of 2 nodes and the weekly tests can scale up to 16 nodes which is the current maximum chosen within the test suite. For more information regarding possible scales, please refer to Deliverable 1.5.

For each of the periodic runs, a ReFrame configuration file describing the system is also required.

Currently, periodic runs are performed on the following clusters:

- Vega (IZUM)
- Karolina (IT4innovations)
- Snellius (SURF)
- Doduo, Donphan, Gallade, Hortense, Shinx, Skitty (UGent)
- BETZY, FRAM, SAGA (Sigma2)
- AWS Magic Castle

All of these clusters run the EESSI test suite on the EESSI software environment, and push their data to the dashboard (discussed more extensively in section 3).

3 Dashboard

3.1 Overview

The developed online dashboard offers an intuitive and straightforward way to visualize test results generated by the EESSI ReFrame test suite. It presents data either as a series of performance metrics (e.g. time series) or as an identity matrix showing test pass rates. The former can be accessed by visiting <https://dashboard.eessi.io>, whereas the latter is integrated into the documentation page on <https://eessi.io/docs/test-suite/dashboard/>. These visual representations of the test results help system administrators and EESSI developers to quickly identify and address inconsistencies in the performance of scientific applications integrated into the EESSI shared software stack.

3.2 Structure

Figure 1: Dashboard ecosystem.

Figure 1 illustrates the generic structure of the dashboard ecosystem. Each vertical layer represents a separate hosting site dedicated to a specific task:

- **HPC site** – an HPC system where the ReFrame tests are executed and test reports are generated.
- **Database Virtual Machine (Database VM)** – a cloud virtual machine that hosts the *Elasticsearch* database where the test data is stored.
- **Dashboard Virtual Machine (Dashboard VM)** – a cloud virtual machine that runs the front-end application with a dashboard.

At the HPC site, test reports from the EESSI ReFrame suite are created and saved in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format. These JSON files are then parsed by a Python [ingestion script](#), which pushes the parsed data into the *Elasticsearch* (ES) database on the Database VM. On the Dashboard VM, an *Elastic* proxy handles queries to the database, retrieving relevant data and making it accessible to the front-end for visualization.

On all participating HPC sites, the ingestion script is scheduled to run daily via a *cron* job. Upon execution, the script scans the designated directory where ReFrame stores its report files, parses each file to extract test metadata, and computes a unique hash value for every test entry. This hash value is generated using the following fields from each test report:

- Timestamp of execution
- Test name
- Hostname
- System name
- ReFrame hash value (unique per run)
- Scheduler assigned job ID (e.g., from SLURM)
- Test elapsed time
- Command line used to run the test

A combination of these fields is hashed using MD5 to create a truly unique identifier for each test that is used by the ingestion script for de-duplication. The script then queries the *Elasticsearch* (ES) database to check for the existence

Figure 2: Dashboard network and security restrictions. The green line indicates full (unrestricted) access, the yellow lines indicate restricted access granted to systems based on their IP addresses, the red line indicates restricted access for the generic public.

of this hash value. If the hash value is not found, the corresponding test data is ingested into the database, otherwise, the entry is skipped.

This mechanism not only excludes the possibility of having duplicates in the database but also ensures fault tolerance of the ingestion step. Thus, if an HPC site temporarily loses connectivity to the database (e.g., due to issues on the Database VM side), previously unprocessed test data will still be ingested during subsequent runs.

The front-end of the dashboard is served as a static Vue application using an Nginx server. The core of the dashboard is developed using the open-source languages and libraries JavaScript, TypeScript, and D3.

3.3 Data storage

To store test results we use *Elasticsearch (ES)*, an open-source distributed search engine and vector database distributed under the Elastic license. The ES instance is installed on Research Cloud at SURF as a Docker container. It contains the main engine – *Elasticsearch (ES)*, and *Kibana*, which provides a convenient web interface for basic data observation, simple user roles management, and permissions adjustments.

Unlike traditional SQL databases, *Elasticsearch (ES)* doesn't require a predefined database schema. The number of parameters and their data types can be adjusted freely at any time, providing greater flexibility. This adaptability reduces constraints on the structure of report files generated by ReFrame, making it easier to develop and maintain the test suite. Moreover, *Elasticsearch (ES)* natively supports the JSON file format, which is the format used by ReFrame to store test reports. This built-in compatibility simplifies both pushing data into the database and retrieving it from the database.

In addition, *Elasticsearch (ES)* is a scalable database, which means it is possible to scale up if the Database VM runs into hardware resource limits. As of May 2025, the database already holds over 115,000 test records, with more than 600 new records added daily from 14 European HPC sites. Thus, the ability to scale up is a key advantage, especially as the number of HPC sites running the EESSI test suite continues to grow, increasing the amount of data that need to be stored.

If needed, the database can be easily migrated to another host by means of a simple mechanism incorporated into the *Elasticsearch (ES)* distribution.

Figure 3: An example view on the dashboard depicting performance time series for the TensorFlow test executed on Snellius “genoa” partition.

3.4 Security

Both the Database VM and Dashboard VM are hosted on SURF Research Cloud (SRC) and run within Docker containers. The use of containers makes these parts of the dashboard ecosystem machine-independent and allows for easy configuration and deployment to any cloud as needed. Access to Database VM and Dashboard VM is limited and controlled by the dashboard administrators to maintain security.

Figure 2 shows the generic dashboard ecosystem, with arrows indicating access levels and access directions. SSH access is restricted to users connected through the SURF VPN, as shown by the green arrows. Only these users can modify the Virtual Machine (VM) settings, migrate the database, add new users, change roles, deploy security certificates, and update the dashboard or *Elasticsearch* instances. These users also have access to ports 80 and 443 on which the database, *Kibana* and front-end are served.

Connections from HPC sites to the Database VM are limited to specific IP addresses listed in the firewall rules (yellow arrows in Figure 2). End-users cannot access the VM unless their IP is explicitly whitelisted. Even then, access is restricted to port 80, which serves only the *Elasticsearch* database and not *Kibana*.

In addition to HPC sites, the backend service running on the Dashboard VM can also access *Elasticsearch* on port 80 of the Database VM (also shown by yellow arrows). The access indicated by yellow lines in Figure 2 requires a dedicated username with read/write permissions and an Application Programming Interface (API) key, both configured per HPC site and per *Dashboard VM*.

The dashboard front-end is served using the *Nginx* server on port 443. This is the only public-facing interface accessible to end users (red arrows in Figure 2).

3.5 Dashboards

3.5.1 Performance as time series

Figure 3 shows the typical view of the dashboard. The left panel provides filtering options, while the plot on the right displays the performance over time. Failed tests are marked with crosses, indicating missing performance data. These points are vertically aligned with the last successful test, and dashed lines connect them to highlight the gap in data.

Test failures can occur for various reasons. The most common is a "sanity error" caused by a canceled job on the HPC site. Cancellations may result from insufficient available resources – such as nodes under maintenance – or from more serious issues affecting the system during the execution of tests.

Ideally, the performance metrics over time should be stable and consistent. Significant deviations usually point to changes in either the HPC site configuration or the test setup. It is the responsibility of system administrators and EESSI test suite developers to detect and address these changes promptly.

Figure 4: Filtering panel with highlighted sections (left) and detailed information about a test point (right).

Figure 5: An example of a beeswarm plot.

Users can investigate specific tests by hovering over a data point or selecting it directly (see Figure 4). Hovering displays a tooltip with detailed test information, whereas selecting a point reveals the full test data in the box below the plot.

The filtering panel (see left part of Figure 4) lets the user control what is displayed on the plot. It has five sub-sections:

1. **Export** – save plots as JPG or PNG files.
2. **Records** – show a number of statistics for the currently loaded test data.
3. **Test selection** – choose which test records to retrieve from the database and specify the time frame.
4. **Plotting** – configure how the loaded data points are displayed.
5. **Filtering** – narrow the focus to a specific subset of data by applying. Data points that do not match the selected filters will be excluded.

For more information about the filters, the end user can click the "question mark" icon located in the top-right corner of each sub-section to view a help message.

3.5.2 Performance as beeswarm

In addition to time series plots, it is also possible to generate beeswarm plots, where all data points are displayed without overlap, clearly illustrating the overall data distribution. To create this type of plot, the user can change the

Figure 8: Identity matrix. Detailed view on the module names over systems.

Site name	Partition	Company (country)
Snellius	rome	SURF (NL)
Snellius	genoa	SURF (NL)
Vega	cpu	IZUM (Slovenia)
Karolina	qcpu	IT4I (Czech Republic)
Skitty	skitty	UGent (Belgium)
Shinx	Shinx	UGent (Belgium)
Hortense	cpu_rome	UGent (Belgium)
Hortense	cpu_rome_512	UGent (Belgium)
Hortense	cpu_milan	UGent (Belgium)
Gallade	gallade	UGent (Belgium)
Donphan	donphan	UGent (Belgium)
Doduo	doduo	UGent (Belgium)
Jotlik	jotlik	UGent (Belgium)
Accelgor	accelgor	UGent (Belgium)
Saga	normal	Sigma2 (Norway)
Saga	bigmem	Sigma2 (Norway)
Fram	normal	Sigma2 (Norway)
Fram	bigmem	Sigma2 (Norway)
Betzy	normal	Sigma2 (Norway)
MagicCastle	aarch64-generic-16c-32gb	AWS
MagicCastle	aarch64-neoverse-N1-16c-32gb	AWS
MagicCastle	aarch64- neoverse-V1-16c32gb	AWS

Table 1: List of HPC sites and clouds presented in the dashboard.

To get more details on the tests, a user can also click on a row to view all module versions used for that specific test (see Figure 8). In this detailed view, columns still represent the HPC systems, but rows now correspond to the specific module versions involved in executing the test.

3.6 Connected systems

Table 1 lists HPC sites and clouds currently sending test data to the database and visible on the dashboard. This list is expected to grow significantly in the future when EESSI is being adopted by more European Tier-1 and Tier-2 HPC systems.

4 Analysis

4.1 Functional verification

The first example of functional testing is the test step that is carried out in the pre-deployment phase to functionally verify the software being ingested as mentioned in deliverable 1.5. Pre-deployment tests are run on the same nodes on which the software was also built. As such, the tests run on all of the supported architectures, thus making sure that the installed software is not only sane but also functional, and integrates correctly with the other components of the software stack such as the underlying MPI libraries and the math libraries.

In the pre-deployment phase, a subset of the tests from the portable test suite are run based on which software is installed. If there is a test available for that software package, it is run. Additionally, a number of independent tests (e.g. on lower level libraries), are always run, regardless of which software was just installed. This is to make sure the installation of the software did not unintentionally break components it should not have touched.

A good example of where pre-deployment testing proved useful was in building GROMINGEN MACHINE for Chemical Simulation (GROMACS) 2024.1. Here, the pre-deployment test for GROMACS was failing due to invalid Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) code being exposed in the kernels on ARM Neoverse V1. This was reported to the GROMACS developers, who then created and released a patch to fix the issue. This illustrates a unique form of software co-design between MultiXscale and the upstream developers, where MultiXscale is able to discover architecture-specific issues (due to the wide range of supported hardware architectures), while upstream developers have the expertise to resolve them. The issue is described here for further technical details: [GROMACS issue](#).

The second example of functional testing is when the tests are run periodically. These tests are carried out on the cloud (AWS cluster) and on EuroHPC machines. The tests can report failures for various reasons here, such as non-availability of the EESSI software stack due to configuration issues or issues with local or central EESSI mirror servers or due to local system problems. The test summaries are available via the dashboard in the form of test identity matrix if the underlying machines have automated the push of test data into the dashboard server. Further analysis can be carried out looking at the detailed logs of the test which are locally available within the system to further shed light on the cause.

Figure 9: Performance (time steps per second, higher is better) vs time for LJ test for Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) application on Vega CPU partition (Rome 7H12) executed on a scale of 2 nodes. Time spans from 01-01-2024 till 01-05-2025. The blue dashed line indicates the mean performance.

4.2 Time series analysis

4.2.1 Performance baseline and variance

Establishing a baseline performance for a given test is generally difficult. For (very) basic synthetic tests (e.g. a bandwidth test), the baseline is typically based on the hardware specifications and firmware settings. However, for application tests, it is near-impossible to determine a theoretical baseline performance. A practical result of the periodic testing is that it provides a clear baseline, which then allows detection of any changes compared to that baseline.

Figure 9 shows the LAMMPS performance over time on Vega's Rome CPU partition. Apart from the mean, which is the baseline performance achieved (in time steps per second), the variance can provide information on the stability of performance of a system. Some tests inherently show a higher variability than others - this is no reason for concern. However, if a test shows substantially higher variability on one system than on others, this may be a reason for the system administrators to investigate, as it may indicate issues with a subset of the nodes, or an overload on shared resources (e.g. parallel filesystem, network congestion etc.).

4.2.2 Performance patterns and implications

Figure 10: Performance (ns per day, higher is better) vs time for GROMACS application benchmark on Snellius CPU partition (Genoa 9654) executed on a scale of 1 node. Time spans from 01-07-2024 till 09-05-2025.

A concrete example of where the dashboard clearly indicated a systematic problem on a system (in this case: Snellius) can be seen in Figure 10. The single node and two node GROMACS performance had dropped during the time period August to September 2024 on the Snellius' genoa CPU partition. This drop in performance was caused by:

- A security mitigation that was applied at the firmware level and which included an upgrade of the operating system from RHEL 8 to RHEL 9. The security mitigation was only applicable on Zen4 hardware, and thus only implemented there.
- Firmware related issues which required a full system reboot.

These problems were identified in the order they are mentioned above. The security mitigation related problem can also be seen in Figure 11 where the performance drop and the recovery after the fix in January 2025 can be clearly identified. It can also be seen from Figure 12 that the drop in performance was not network related since the internode performance didn't show any degradation. It is to be noted that some data of the OSU tests is missing here, most likely because the tests were not running. The firmware related problem was fixed in February 2025 and once the system was rebooted, the GROMACS performance returned to normal.

A factor that also has an effect on performance is the binding of Message Passing Interface (MPI) ranks and OpenMP threads. In the release of the test suite during July 2024, proper binding was enforced within the test suite for the

Figure 11: Bandwidth (MB per second, higher is better) vs time for point to point test for OSU Microbenchmarks application on Snellius CPU partition (Genoa 9654) executed within a node. Time spans from 01-01-2024 till 01-03-2025.

systems by distinguishing systems where hyper-threading is enabled and where it is not. If hyper-threading is enabled, then the tests can be written such that one can pin a task on each hardware thread or on each physical core based on the option that is chosen in the test. This change was adopted in the Vega system later around August 2024 and a stark improvement in Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems (ESPResSo) performance (lower is better) can be seen in Figures 13 and 14. In the ESPResSo test, one task per physical core is chosen due to which the number of tasks per node was halved. The pinning also resulted in a more consistent performance (less variance), which can be clearly seen in the figures. The reduction in variance can also be attributed to less OS jitter and cache misses compared to the situation where all hyper-threads were occupied by the migrating MPI processes.

4.3 Hardware based comparison

An important utility of this system is to compare the performance across various systems, including the cloud. It is important to note that the test suite is not fine-tuned to achieve maximum performance on a given system (it is not a benchmark suite), but the tests are designed to show indicative performance on all systems since the same tests are run on each system. The reasons we call it indicative are the following:

- The software installed within the EESSI software stack is optimized for that hardware.
- The pinning of the MPI tasks can be controlled within individual tests via the functions present in the Mixin class which in turn controls the scheduler options using environment variables. This can be at the thread level (assuming hyper-threading is enabled), physical CPU level or the socket level.

This rich overview gives the user an indication as to which hardware their application performs the best. Several tier 0, 1 and 2 systems running on similar hardware should also get an indication if the applications within their systems perform optimally on a given set of hardware. If not, then they can approach the respective system maintainers or administrators to exchange information regarding the settings that each of them applies to achieve this, which promotes further collaboration.

As an example, the Tensorflow application from the test suite executed on various CPU partitions is shown in Figures 15 and 16. Here we also compare performance on various ARM architectures available on AWS cluster. Even with Ethernet based interconnect, the performance almost doubles from one to two nodes, which shows that the test itself is not network dependent but is more memory dependent with highest performance reported on Snellius-genoa partition which has a AMD Zen4 based architecture. Another interesting point is that the CPU partitions Karolina-qcpu, Vega and Snellius-rome have the same CPU hardware, namely AMD 7H12 but interestingly the average performance is different, Vega performing 15 percent better some times on a single node but on two nodes the Snellius-rome per-

Figure 12: Bandwidth (MB per second, higher is better) vs time for point to point test for OSU Microbenchmarks application on Snellius CPU partition (Genoa 9654) executed across 2 nodes. Time spans from 01-01-2024 till 01-03-2025.

formance seems to be the best (apart from a few blips due to system related issues). This could be due to differences in clock frequencies set by the system admins and may also be due to differences in network hardware employed by the systems.

Figure 13: Performance (seconds per step, lower is better) vs time for the P3M test for ESPResSo application on Vega CPU partition (Rome 7H12) executed on 1 node. Time spans from 01-01-2024 till 04-01-2025.

Figure 14: Performance (seconds per step, lower is better) vs time for the LJ test for ESPResSo application on Vega CPU partition (Rome 7H12) executed on 1 node. Time spans from 01-01-2024 till 04-01-2025.

Figure 15: Performance (images per second, higher is better) vs time for TensorFlow application on various CPU partitions on the cloud (AWS), EuroHPC systems (Vega and Karolina), Snellius (Dutch Tier-1 system) executed on 1 node. Time spans from 01-01-2025 till 19-05-2025.

Figure 16: Performance (images per second, higher is better) vs time for TensorFlow application on various CPU partitions on the cloud (AWS), EuroHPC systems (Vega and Karolina), Snellius (Dutch Tier-1 system) executed on 2 nodes. Time spans from 01-01-2025 till 19-05-2025.

5 Conclusion and outlook

A functional test setup and pipeline is developed, deploying the test suite developed within Task 1.3 in a periodic manner, across various Tier 0, Tier 1 and Tier 2 systems. The pipeline involves pushing the results of the performed test into a public dashboard. The test results in this dashboard provide value not only to maintainers of the EESSI shared software stack, but also to system administrators and end-users. As illustrated by the examples in this deliverable, the dashboard can be used to monitor problems within the EESSI software stack, but also identify issues in the underlying systems themselves, which can then be resolved by the respective system administrators.

References

Acronyms used

AWS	Amazon Web Services
CI	Continuous Integration
EESSI	European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
HPC	High Performance Computing
MPI	Message Passing Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
EuroHPC	European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
VM	Virtual Machine
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
Database VM	Database Virtual Machine
Dashboard VM	Dashboard Virtual Machine
ES	Elasticsearch
SRC	SURF Research Cloud
API	Application Programming Interface

Software mentioned

ESPResSo	Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems
GROMACS	GROningen MACHine for Chemical Simulation
LAMMPS	Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator

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